

Database structure and meaning of filenames for the **euroclim500** dataset

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<http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/browse/badc/euroclim500/data/HadCM3/>

Experiment name : For more information: see slide 3

Ensemble number

Time period

Variable name: see slides 4-7

Name	Years (C.E.)	Ensembles	Forcings						
			Solar	Volcs	GHGs	LUSE	AER	O ₃	Orb
All	800-2000	r1	✓	✓	✓	✓	>1820	✓	✓
DRIFT (CTRL850)	800-2000	r1	850	800- 850	800-850	825	0	PI	825
SOLAR SHAPIRO	800-2000	r1	✓ Shapiro	800- 850	800-850	825	0	PI	825
All	1400-2000	r2,3,4	✓	✓	✓	✓	>1820	✓	✓
Solar	1400-2000	r1,2,3,4	✓	0	1400	1400	0	PI	1400
VOLC	1400-2000	r1,2,3	1400	✓	1400	1400	0	PI	1400
GHG	1400-2000	r1,2,3,4	1400	0	✓	1400	0	PI	1400
NoLUSE	1400-2000	r1,2,3,4	✓	✓	✓	1400	>1820	✓	✓
NoAER	1750-2000	r1,2,3,4	✓	✓	✓	✓	0	✓	✓

Details of experimental design. A tick indicates where the simulations included the forcing for the whole time period. Where a single year or range is given the forcing was constant at the year or range. PI is pre-industrial ozone. The solar forcing is Steinhilber/Wang unless otherwise stated. For more detail see forcing documentation

Daily mean atmospheric variables

apa

Variable Name	Meaning
cvrain	CONVECTIVE RAINFALL RATE KG/M2/S
cvsnow	CONVECTIVE SNOWFALL RATE KG/M2/S
htinst	GEOPOTENTIAL HEIGHT: PRESSURE LEVELS
lsrain	LARGE SCALE RAINFALL RATE KG/M2/S
lssnow	LARGE SCALE SNOWFALL RATE KG/M2/S
m1s1i235	TOTAL DOWNWARD SURFACE SW FLUX
pinst	PRESSURE AT MEAN SEA LEVEL
precip	TOTAL PRECIPITATION RATE KG/M2/S
rh	RELATIVE HUMIDITY AT 1.5M
sm	SOIL MOISTURE CONTENT
snowdepth	SNOW AMOUNT AFTER TIMESTEP KG/M2
taux	X-COMP OF SURF & BL WIND STRESS N/M2
tauy	Y-COMP OF SURF & BL WIND STRESS N/M2
temp	TEMPERATURE AT 1.5M
tempmax	MAX TEMPERATURE AT 1.5M
tempmin	MIN TEMPERATURE AT 1.5M
wind	10 METRE WIND SPEED M/S
windmax	MAX 10 METRE WIND SPEED M/S
wme	WIND MIXING EN'GY FLUX INTO SEA W/M2

All other atmospheric variables

apm, aps, apy

Variable Name	Meaning
QCF	CLOUD ICE CONTENT AFTER DYNAM CLOUD
QCL	CLOUD LIQUID WATER AFTER DYN CLOUD
blht	BOUNDARY LAYER DEPTH AFTER TIMESTEP
botmelt	HEAT FLUX THROUGH SEA ICE (GBM) W/M2
cldamount	LAYER CLOUD AMOUNT IN EACH LAYER
convcld13	CONV CLOUD AMOUNT AFTER TIMESTEP
convcld212	CONV. CLOUD AMOUNT ON EACH MODEL LEV
csilr	CLEAR-SKY (II) DOWN SURFACE LW FLUX
csolr	CLEAR-SKY (II) UPWARD LW FLUX (TOA)
cvrain	CONVECTIVE RAINFALL RATE KG/M2/S
cvsnow	CONVECTIVE SNOWFALL RATE KG/M2/S
evap	EVAPORATION FROM SEA (GBM) KG/M2/S
ht	GEOPOTENTIAL HEIGHT: PRESSURE LEVELS
iceconc	SEA ICE FRACTION AFTER TIMESTEP
icedepth	SEA ICE DEPTH (MEAN OVER ICE) M
ilr207	DOWNWARD LW RAD FLUX: SURFACE
ilr238	TOTAL DOWNWARD LW FLUX AT THE TROP.
lh	SURFACE LATENT HEAT FLUX W/M2
longwave201	NET DOWN SURFACE LW RAD FLUX
longwave203	NET DOWN LW RAD FLUX: OPEN SEA
longwave237	NET DOWNWARD LW FLUX AT THE TROP.
lsrain	LARGE SCALE RAINFALL RATE KG/M2/S
lssnow	LARGE SCALE SNOWFALL RATE KG/M2/S
m1s0i16	CONV CLOUD LIQUID WATER PATH

Variable Name	Meaning
m1s13i201	QT SOURCE/SINK IN QT_POS KG/M2/S
m1s14i201	ATMOS ENERGY CORR'N IN COLUMN W/M2
m1s1i207	INCOMING SW RAD FLUX (TOA): ALL TSS
m1s1i208	OUTGOING SW RAD FLUX (TOA)
m1s1i209	CLEAR-SKY (II) UPWARD SW FLUX (TOA)
m1s1i210	CLEAR-SKY (II) DOWN SURFACE SW FLUX
m1s1i211	CLEAR-SKY (II) UP SURFACE SW FLUX
m1s1i235	TOTAL DOWNWARD SURFACE SW FLUX
m1s1i238	UPWARD SW FLUX AT THE TROP.
m1s2i204	TOTAL CLOUD AMOUNT IN LW RADIATION
m1s3i202	HT FLUX FROM SURF TO DEEP SOIL LEV 1
m1s3i223	SURF & BL TOTL MOISTURE FLUX KG/M2/S
m1s3i223lon2	SURF & BL TOTL MOISTURE FLUX KG/M2/S
m1s3i258	SURFACE SNOWMELT HEAT FLUX W/M2
m1s3i259	CANOPY CONDUCTANCE M/S
m1s3i261	GROSS PRIMARY PRODUCTIVITY KG C/M2/S
m1s3i262	NET PRIMARY PRODUCTIVITY KG C/M2/S
m1s3i263	PLANT RESPIRATION KG/M2/S
m1s3i296	EVAP FROM SOIL SURF : RATE KG/M2/S
m1s3i297	EVAP FROM CANOPY : RATE KG/M2/S
m1s3i298	SUBLIM. SURFACE (GBM) : RATE KG/M2/S
m1s3i299	TRANSPIRATION RATE KG/M2/S
m1s5i234	GRIDBOX MEAN CONV. CLOUD WATER PATH
m1s8i202	LAND SNOW MELT HEAT FLUX W/M2

All other atmospheric variables (continued)

apm, aps, apy

Variable Name	Meaning
m1s8i209	CANOPY WATER CONTENT
m1s8i229	UNFROZEN SOIL MOISTURE FRACTION
m1s8i230	FROZEN SOIL MOISTURE FRACTION
m1s8i233	CANOPY THROUGHFALL RATE KG/M2/S
m1s8i234	SURFACE RUNOFF RATE KG/M2/S
m1s8i235	SUB-SURFACE RUNOFF RATE KG/M2/S
olr	OUTGOING LW RAD FLUX (TOA)
omega	OMEGA ON MODEL LEVELS
p	PRESSURE AT MEAN SEA LEVEL
precip	TOTAL PRECIPITATION RATE KG/M2/S
ps	PSTAR AFTER TIMESTEP
q10z1	SPECIFIC HUMIDITY AFTER TIMESTEP
q237z11	SPECIFIC HUMIDITY AT 1.5M
qz2hybs10z2	SPECIFIC HUMIDITY AFTER TIMESTEP
rain	TOTAL RAINFALL RATE: LS+CONV KG/M2/S
rh204	RELATIVE HUMIDITY ON PRESSURE LEVELS
rh245	RELATIVE HUMIDITY AT 1.5M
sh217z9	SURFACE & B.LAYER HEAT FLUXES W/M2
sh228z0	SURFACE SH FLUX FROM SEA (GBM) W/M2
shlon2217z10	SURFACE & B.LAYER HEAT FLUXES W/M2
sm208	SOIL MOISTURE CONTENT
sm223	SOIL MOISTURE CONTENT IN A LAYER
solar_201	NET DOWN SURFACE SW FLUX: SW TS ONLY
solar_203	NET DOWN SW RAD FLUX: OPEN SEA

Variable Name	Meaning
solar_204	NET DOWN SURFACE SW FLUX BELOW 690NM
solar_237	NET DOWNWARD SW FLUX AT THE TROP.
snow	TOTAL SNOWFALL RATE: LS+CONV KG/M2/S
snowdepth	SNOW AMOUNT AFTER TIMESTEP KG/M2
soiltemp	DEEP SOIL TEMPERATURE AFTER B.LAYER
taux219z9	X-COMP OF SURF & BL WIND STRESS N/M2
tauxlon3219z10	X-COMP OF SURF & BL WIND STRESS N/M2
tauy220z9	Y-COMP OF SURF & BL WIND STRESS N/M2
tauylon3220z10	Y-COMP OF SURF & BL WIND STRESS N/M2
temp203	TEMPERATURE ON PRESSURE LEVELS
temp236	TEMPERATURE AT 1.5M
temp24	SURFACE TEMPERATURE AFTER TIMESTEP
theta	THETA AFTER TIMESTEP
topmelt	SEAICE TOP MELTING LH FLUX(GBM) W/M2
u201	U COMPNT OF WIND ON PRESSURE LEVELS
u225	10 METRE WIND U-COMP
u2	U COMPNT OF WIND AFTER TIMESTEP
v202	V COMPNT OF WIND ON PRESSURE LEVELS
v226	10 METRE WIND V-COMP
v3	V COMPNT OF WIND AFTER TIMESTEP
wind	10 METRE WIND SPEED M/S
wme	WIND MIXING EN'GY FLUX INTO SEA W/M2

Oceanic variables

opm, ops, opy

Variable Name	Meaning
HTN162	HTN:NONPEN.HT.FLX*LF INTO OCN W/M2 A
HTN206	GBM HTN INTO OCEAN BUDGET W/M**2
HTN214	GBM HTN INTO ICE BUDGET W/M**2
HTN217	GBM HTN INTO OCN WHERE ICY W/M**2
HTN218	GBM SNOWDEPTH ON SEA-ICE M
PLE	PLE:PRECIP-EVAP INTO OCEAN KG/M2/S A
SOL	SOL: PEN.SOLAR*LF INTO OCEAN W/M2 A
TAUX	TAUX: X_WINDSTRESS N/M2 A
TAUY	TAUY: Y_WINDSTRESS N/M2 A
WME	WME: WIND MIXING ENERGY FLUX W/M2 A
W	VERT.VEL. ON OCEAN HALF LEVELS CM/S
botmelt	GBM SEAICE BOTMELT HEAT FLUX W/M2 A
iceconc	AICE : ICE CONCENTRATION
icedepth	HICE: MEAN ICE DEPTH OVER GRIDBOX M
m2s0i130	STREAMFUNCTION (OCEAN) CM3/S
m2s0i132	STREAMFN TENDENCY (OCEAN) CM3/S/TS
m2s0i137	MIXED LAYER DEPTH (OCEAN) M
m2s0i142	GBM CARYHEAT MISC HEAT FLX(ICE) W/M2
m2s0i143	GBM HEAT FLUX:OCEAN TO ICE(OCN) W/M2
m2s0i144	RATE OF SALINITY CHANGE (ICE) PSU/S
m2s0i186	P-E FLUX CORRECTION KG/M2/S A
m2s0i194	THICKNESS DIFF COEFF (OCEAN) CM2/S
m2s30i208	CARYHEAT AFTER ROW CALCULATION W/M2
m2s30i246	BAROCLINIC X-ACCN (ZUN) CM/S**2
m2s30i247	BAROCLINIC Y-ACCN (ZVN) CM/S**2
m2s30i279	ANOM. HEAT "SINK" AT OCN FLOOR W/M2

Variable Name	Meaning
m2s30i280	WATER_FLUX*SALINITY/DENSITY m Gs**-1
m2s30i281	GM EDDY U VELOCITY (OCEAN)
m2s30i282	GM EDDY V VELOCITY (N FACE) (OCEAN)
m2s30i283	GM EDDY W VEL (TOP FACE) (OCEAN)
m2s30i320	TOTAL OCEAN U-VELOCITY CM S**-1
m2s30i321	TOTAL OCEAN V-VELOCITY CM S**-1
m2s32i209	U COMPONENT OF ICE VELOCITY (M.S-1)
m2s32i210	V COMPONENT OF ICE VELOCITY (M.S-1)
m2s32i223	d/dt AICE DYNAMICS s-1
m2s32i224	d/dt HICE DYNAMICS m s-1
m2s32i225	d/dt GBM SNOWDEPTH DYNAMICS m s-1
m2s32i226	d/dt HICE DIFFUSION m s-1
m2s32i227	d/dt AICE THERMODYN s-1
m2s32i228	d/dt HICE THERMODYN m s-1
m2s32i229	d/dt GBM SNOWDEPTH THERMODYN m s-1
outflow	RIVER OUTFLOW INTO OCEAN KG/M2/S A
salinity	SALINITY (OCEAN) (PSU-35)/1000
snowdepth	SNOW DEPTH (OCEAN) M
snowfall171	SNOWFALL INTO OCN/ONTO ICE KG/M2/S A
snowfall207	SNOWRATE WHERE NO ICE KG M**-2 S**-1
snowfall215	SNOWRATE WHERE ICY KG M**-2 S**-1
sublim	SUBLIMATION FROM SEAICE KG/M2/S A
temp	POTENTIAL TEMPERATURE (OCEAN) DEG.C
topmelt	GBM SEAICE TOPMELT HEAT FLUX W/M2 A
ucurr	BAROCLINIC U_VELOCITY (OCEAN) CM/S
vcurr	BAROCLINIC V_VELOCITY (OCEAN) CM/S